

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№3

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 72 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 11-martda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Improving the efficiency of investment activity in oil and gas enterprises.....	24
Raxmatova M.G., G'ofurov Sh.N.	
Organization of control and evaluation of effectiveness in international companies.....	30
Nasimov Bakhtiyor Vasiyevich	
Xalqaro standartlarning korxonalar eksportini oshirishdagi ahamiyati.....	35
Sobitov Diyor Abbralxonovich	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalar boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	40
Ataimatov Iqboljon Zumratjonovich	
Xorazm viloyatida turizm infratuzilmasini innovatsion rivojlantirish ko'rsatkichlarini ekonometrik modellashtirish va prognozlashtirishning ba'zi masalalari.....	46
Jumaniyazova Ro'za Quvondiq qizi	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy barqarorligini mustahkamlash.....	60
Rasulov Muxammad Bobur Fazliddin o'g'li	
Economic analysis of investment activity of enterprises.....	66
Shermatov Akhror Abduhakimovich	

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY OF ENTERPRISES

Shermatov Akhror Abduhakimovich

Teacher of the Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Abstract: The relationship between investment activities at firms is scientifically studied, several scientific approaches to the idea of investment are developed, and an economic analysis of investment activity at enterprises is presented in this article. As a complicated component structure, the study successfully covers the production indicators of industrial production firms.

Key words: investment, enterprise, system, economic efficiency, industrial investment activity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada korxonalarning investitsiya faoliyati iqtisodiy tahlil qilingan, investitsiya tushunchasiga berilgan turli xil ilmiy yondashuvlar yoritilgan hamda korxonlardagi investitsion faoliyatning aloqadorligi ilmiy jihatdan o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotda sanoat ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining ishlab chiqarish ko'rsatkichlari murakkab tarkibiy tuzilma sifatida samarali tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: investitsiya, korxon, tizim, iqtisodiy samaradorlik, sanoat investitsion faoliyati.

Аннотация: В статье дается экономический анализ инвестиционной деятельности предприятий, а также научно исследуется важность инвестиционной деятельности предприятий. Исследование хорошо показывает, что производственные показатели промышленных предприятий сложны.

Ключевые слова: инвестиции, предприятие, система, экономическая эффективность, производственно-инвестиционная деятельность.

INTRODUCTION

Economic analysis of business investment activities is crucial, and by drawing conclusions from the analysis, the business can use the information to inform strategic choices for the years to come. Qualitative analysis enables strategic decision-making, diversification in different areas of activity to lower the level of risks, and the anticipation, identification, and elimination of different levels of dangers and risks that may develop in the enterprise's activities. In the end, these steps might help to lower the amount of different losses that businesses might sustain during emergencies and avoid going bankrupt. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, stated in his January 24, 2020, address to the Oliy Majlis of the country that public-private partnership mechanisms, which are one of the most effective ways to draw in investments, should be widely implemented in areas like transportation, energy, roads, utilities, healthcare, and education. Furthermore, programs to modernize and boost competitiveness in 12 key industrial sectors are being expedited, and deep structural reforms have been initiated in a number of other sectors, including energy, oil and gas, geology, transportation, road construction, agriculture and water management, drinking water and heat supply, and many more. In 2019, industrial production was reported to have grown by 6.6%. [1]

The volume of fixed assets keeps growing as a result of industrial firms' modernization, technical and technological renewal, and the commissioning of new ones. Economic analysis is a sophisticated study that integrates several facets of a certain economic entity's operations and is conducted using a comprehensive, systematized fundamental approach, methodologies, and theories. As a consequence of the analysis, it is recognized that, in addition to providing the chance to evaluate the entity's operations from specific perspectives, the study's findings can be effectively applied to future decision-making.

Finding economic relationships that are directly related to the entity's operations, identifying potential issues in each of these relationships and their best solutions, carrying out particular or independently defined tasks using specialized methods, techniques, and guidelines in the analysis of this process, identifying potential future problem cases, and formulating suitable decisions to eliminate them are all steps in the economic analysis process. Using a dialectical approach, it is crucial to maintain the integrity of the analysis and synthesis techniques, which are scientific study methods of actual realities [9]. Priority directions for the enterprise's investment operations are established in order to accomplish long-term objectives when creating a development strategy for the next periods.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

By the 1980s, the term “investment” in economic literature was not used in the practice of analyzing the process of socialist reproduction and was mainly cited only in economic studies by foreign economists. It should be emphasized that the concept of “investment activity”, differing from the content of capital investments, was used in a much narrower sense than investment. In particular, capital investments can also be made in other types of economic resources: information resources, securities, commodity material reserves and human capital. Foreign economists of the 19th century, such as J. Keynes, J. Clark, R. Harrod, S. Fisher, R. Dornbusch, R. Schmalenzi [8; 12; 11], also made a worthy contribution to the development of research related to investment activity.

We can see from researching theoretical approaches to investment that both domestic and international economists have attempted to characterize it from a variety of angles. For instance, the interpretation of investment as an economic category explains the economic linkages related to the movement of the value of fixed capital as a process describing the value of fixed capital in the circular movement of reproduction [10]. It is easy to comprehend that the substance of investments as a process-related approach has a wider significance based on the methods used by a group of economists. Because the cyclical movement of repeating production’s value movement demonstrates that investments raise both circulating assets and fixed capital. Additionally, the strategy was based on the introduction and completion of the investment period stage into fixed capital and productive forces, and the enlarged movement of repeated production was examined. The expenses of fixed assets in repeated production, as well as their development and modernization, are closely tied to the cost-effective method in theoretical perspectives on the concept of “investment.” Theoretically, this approach’s concepts are tied to real-world activities that mostly functioned inside the framework of the economic mechanism controlled by the administrative-competency-competitive economy.

The difficulty of maintaining the stability of commodity-money relations has gotten worse as a result of society’s reproduction process. Additionally, the administrative-command system’s overall management efficiency has decreased, and the resource approach to investing has become more prevalent. The theory of investment resources is the foundation of the resource approach. In this sense, we believe that investments are monetary expenditures on the reproduction’s fixed assets. The static nature of the examination of investing activity as an object limits the drawbacks of both techniques. The scope of study on investments as a whole market area is likewise constrained by the cost and resource approaches.

According to J. Keynes, a classical economist, investment is defined as a portion of unconsumed income, or the present rise in property worth brought about by productive activity within a specific time period [8]. Investment is defined in contemporary economic theory as spending money on commodities, services, and real capital (such as machinery, equipment, and industrial facilities) [6]. «Investment is a method of investing capital that guarantees the efficiency of income and the preservation of the value of capital or is aimed at increasing its value,» according to international economists Lawrence J. Gitman and Michael D. Jonk [7]. «Investments are monetary investments for the purpose of preserving and increasing capital,» according to some economists. [2] The methodologies and viewpoints of the majority of economists about the nature of investments do not significantly alter if we examine the ensuing interpretations. Our scientific investigation led us to the conclusion that this kind of interpretation of investments is limited and cannot adequately convey their economic substance and essence.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

After all, investments have their own content and shape and are not thought of as just consisting of expenses methodology for research. This study examined and categorized the scientific methodologies used in empirical and conceptual studies pertaining to investment analysis that were mirrored in scientific sources across several online databases. Additionally, the study employed grouping techniques, comparative analysis, historically and logic, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, systematic analysis, and monographic analysis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Effective investment placement, implementation, and administration at any level of the organization’s economic management include investment activity. Regardless of future development strategy, investment activity is one of the key components of an economic system for any economic institution, regardless of size or degree. We believe that the following description of these processes may be made using the state and business example (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Description of functional aspects of investment activity at all levels of the economic system.

A complicated economic system for the business is created by the intricate and interwoven structural framework of investment activity. Thus, while examining the economic operations of businesses, contemporary economists employ a systemic approach. The process of studying the firm is closely tied to the process of assessing the overall economic system since economic analysis tools are used to analyze all the relationships associated with economic activity.

Additionally, the study of our companies' investing activity is intimately tied to this process. First and foremost, these procedures provide the mechanism for carrying out an economic study of the enterprise's overall structural framework. The example image of the enterprise's economic activity in the microenvironment shows this.

All physical and legal companies, as well as government agencies that deal with businesses, make up these structural units. This indicates the interdependence and connectivity of the actual and financial sectors of the national economy. Thus, it can be said that the financial sector and the real sector's investment activity process are tightly related. The primary goals of the examination of an enterprise's investment activity are represented by the capital investment position in the enterprise as a complex structural structure of the economic system (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The relationship between the investment activity of the enterprise and the structures of the external environment.

The objectives are to:

- raise the enterprise's market value and the amount of future revenue it will generate for its owners;
- boost the effectiveness of investments drawn to the business;
- guarantee the enterprise's liquidity, solvency, and financial stability by conducting an analysis of investment activities and maintaining ongoing control over these indicators;
- raise the net present value of investment projects; maximize funding sources for investments;
- and make strategic decisions regarding the prompt identification of investment risks and their efficient management.

Generally speaking, there are two ways to look at the process of carrying out an analysis of investment activities based on the responsibilities mentioned above.

These include raising the degree of investment attractiveness and managing the analysis of investment operations. These domains are interrelated systems that analyze business economic activity and investment activity (Figure 3).

Figure 3. To the enterprise as a complex structural structure of the economic system efficient deployment of capital.

On the other hand, the second direction of investment analysis is related to financial analysis and involves the process of examining investments that the company has drawn from outside sources, such as securities, loans, and capital investments made by insurance companies [3].

Any prominent business in developed nations maintains and controls its ownership rights. The IPO (Initial Public Offering) process determines the degree of integration of ownership relations, the environment and conditions created the enterprise's level of investment appeal, the issuance of additional shares, and the sale of long-term securities regardless of their market value.

It should be underlined that the organizational and structural makeup of the enterprise's whole financial resources has a direct impact on how well investment activities are implemented. Additionally, the enterprise's manufacturing process is momentarily accelerated by financial resources. The firm faces severe repercussions when financial resources are used inefficiently and issues resulting from the analysis of investment activities are not promptly monitored and resolved. The company's working and fixed capital will depreciate if it doesn't engage in investment operations. Promising profits will be achieved in addition to the replenishment of fixed capital through the qualitative execution of investment operations. Consequently, the enterprise's prospective long-term development is guaranteed.

The industry's part of GDP has been sharply increasing over the past few years, if we look at the operations of the industrial firms that are the subject of our investigation. Specifically, if this metric was 20.2 percent in 2010, it was about 28.1 percent in 2021. Naturally, the industry's dramatic rise in output volume and its ability to draw in capital had an impact. Specifically, if we examine the dynamics of shifts in industry production volume between 2010 and 2021, the growth was, on average, about 5.5%.

Furthermore, if we look at the amount of money invested in industry, namely ferrous metallurgy companies, this figure was 530.6 billion sums in 2010 and nearly 678.9 billion sums in 2021. The creation of a system that

allows the business to efficiently reinvest its revenues will boost its future competitiveness in the market and result in the efficient turnover of idle capital.

An analysis of the dynamics of changes in industrial enterprises' net profits by economic activity type is shown in this table. According to this indicator, the net profit of processing industrial enterprises was 3439.8 billion soums in 2014 and 7176.9 billion soums in 2021 (Table 1).

Table 1. Analysis of industrial production indicators in the Republic of Uzbekistan¹.

Years	of industry in GDP share, in %	Industrial production volume dynamics, in %	Ferrous metallurgical industry investment in enterprises volume, million soums
2010	20.2	105.9	530644,9
2011	18.7	104.4	535033,4
2012	19.3	105.7	524805,1
2013	19.7	107.5	627248,0
2014	20.2	104.5	662169,6
2015	20.2	105.3	524772,3
2016	20.6	105.4	804273,6
2017	22.2	105.2	1529159,6
2018	26.5	110.8	4559413,1
2019	30.0	105.0	9011829,2
2020	28.5	100.7	6572241,3
2021	28.1	106.2	6789693,4

Source: Developed by the author based on data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In 2021, the total net profit of mining companies was 118.3 billion soums, compared to 2612.4 billion soums in 2017. Industrial businesses' overall financial statistics show that they made 4259.5 billion soums in net profits in 2014. This figure has climbed fivefold in recent years (Table 2).

Table 2. Financial results of industrial enterprises by types of economic activity (net profit, billion soums).

	2015 y	2016 y	2017 y	2018 y	2019 y	2020 y	2021 y
Mining and open pits work	2643,3	2652,4	2612,4	392,6	392,6	224,8	118,3
Processing industry	3645,1	4804,7	7950,5	20642,4	20642,4	5814,2	7176,9
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	160,6	-122,2	-727,9	-787,8	-787,8	67,3	332,3
Water supply, sewage system, waste collection and disposal industry	11,3	24,2	209,9	-141,6	-141,6	10,9	11,2

Source: Developed by the author based on data from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Research indicates that when industrial businesses' net profits rise, more money is required to finance their investment operations. Generally speaking, the following goals guide businesses' available capital (investments):

- the acquisition and implementation of new facilities, equipment, and technical resources;
- the funding of fresh, creative concepts;
- the building and commissioning of new buildings and structures;

¹ <https://qalampir.uz/news/2021-2023-yillarda-yaimning-asosiy-ulushi-k-aysi-tarmok-larga-tugri-keladi-29356>

- the maintenance, modernization, and re-equipment of fixed assets;
- the diversification of product offerings and the opening of new markets;
- and the recurring improvement of staff qualifications

One characteristic of the investment activities of industrial processing enterprises is that they are made in the form of real investments; financing of investment activities through other types of investments is uncommon in practice [4]. When financing the investment activities of industrial enterprises, it is advisable to proceed from the investment activity and its specific features. Investment activity is defined as an activity that is solely related to the processes of implementing investments, and it is crucial to spend relatively large amounts of funds for investment activities in order to obtain a profit or other beneficial effect.

There were 70.6 thousand industrial businesses and organizations as of January 1, 2020, a 124.1% growth over the same period the previous year. The manufacturing (processing) sector grew by 124.4% (share in total industry 94.6%), followed by mining and open pit mining by 129.5% (share in total industry 3.3%), electricity, steam, power supply, and air conditioning by 119.8% (share in total industry 0.5%), and water supply, sewage system, and waste disposal by 105.0% (share in total industry 1.6%). These factors are the primary drivers of the increase in the overall number of industrial enterprises and organizations.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A thorough evaluation of businesses' investment operations and the creation of new plans for the future are made possible by the thorough economic analysis of investment activities provided in this study. It should be underlined that businesses founded on the idea of lean production are now acknowledged as major corporations both domestically and internationally. This satisfies current needs, such as the necessity for us to conduct factor analyses that serve as the foundation for any scientific research project and practically assess the enterprise's worth and reputation. It should not be overlooked that the development of a contemporary market economy and the production of novel goods and services necessitate the application of all the analytical techniques mentioned.

List of used literature

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020. <https://www.uza.uz>
2. Аскинадзи В.М. Investments: a textbook for universities / V. M. Askinadzi, V. F. Maksimova. - 2nd ed. revised and enlarged. - M.: Publishing house "Yurait", 2020. - 385 p.
3. Astanakulov, O. (2020). National projects and government programmes: functional algorithm for evaluating and modelling using the Data Science methodology. *Economic Annals-XXI*, 183(5-6), 51-59. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21003/ea.V183-05>.
4. Astanakulov, O., Asatullaev, Kh., Saidaxmedova, N., & Batirova, N. (2021). The energy efficiency of the national economy assessment in terms of investment in green energy. *Economic Annals-XXI*, 189(5-6(1)), 26-34. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21003/ea.V189-03> 94 Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim / 2022-yil 6-son INNOVATSIYA VA INVESTITSIYA
5. Astanakulov, O.T., Raximov, M.Y., Kalandarova, N.N. (2020). Analysis of The Investment Program of The Analytical Cycle at the Enterprise for the Development of the Company's Entrepreneurial Activity. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, Vol: 26 Issue: 3S, 1528 2686. (Scopus) Retrieved from <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/analysis-of-the-investment-program-of-the-analytical-cycle-at-the-enterprise-for-the-development-of-the-companys-entrepreneurial-a-9736.html>
6. Борисов Е.Ф. Anthology of economic theory. – M.: Jurist, – 2000. – 536 p.
7. Гитман Л.Д., Джонк М.Д. Investing Basics. – M.: Дело, 1999. - 1008 с.
8. Кейнс Дж.М. General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money. *Classics of Economic Science – XX Century.* – Moscow: Gelios ARV, 2020. – p. 229.
9. Любушин Н.П. Economic analysis: textbook – M.: UNITY-DANA, 2012.
10. Г.П., Киселева Н.В. Investment activity. – M.: Knorus, 2005
11. Темирова З.У., Темирболатова С.Х. A teaching aid on the subject "History of Economic Doctrines" for students of the OFO-ZFO studying in the training program 38.05.01 "Economic Security", specializing in "Economic and Legal Support of Economic Security". - Cherkessk: BIC SevKavGGTA, 2018
12. Харрод Р.Ф. Towards the Theory of Economic Dynamics. *Classics of Economic Thought.* - M.: Direct-Media, 2007.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>